

Verification of Photonuclear Reactions in OpenMC with MCNPx and FLUKA

Lorenzo Loi^{1,2}, Andrea Missaglia¹, Carolina Introiini¹, Francesca C. Giacobbo¹, Enrico Padovani¹,
Antonio Cammi^{1,2,3,4,*}

¹Politecnico di Milano, Department of Energy, Via La Masa 34, Milano 20133, Italy;

²INFN, Sezione di Milano Bicocca, 20126 Milan, Italy; ³Department of Mechanical and Nuclear Engineering, Khalifa University, Abu Dhabi, 127788, United Arab Emirates;

⁴Emirates Nuclear Technology Centre (ENTC), Khalifa University of Science and Technology, Abu Dhabi, 127788, United Arab Emirates

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ABSTRACT

The modeling of photonuclear physics is critical for emerging applications in accelerator technology as well as in medical physics and fusion. While the open-source Monte Carlo code OpenMC has well-verified photoatomic models, its photonuclear capabilities are not yet part of an official release. This paper presents a code-to-code verification of the photonuclear physics implemented in a development branch of OpenMC, comparing its performance against the established codes MCNPx and FLUKA. The “broomstick problem”, a canonical benchmark, was used to isolate single-collision photonuclear reactions in ²³⁸U, ⁹Be, and ²H targets. The results demonstrate excellent agreement between OpenMC and MCNPx in both integrated reaction rates, including (γ, n) , $(\gamma, 2n)$, and (γ, F) , and total particle currents across all test cases, using the ENDF7u library. FLUKA, on the other hand, exhibited notable discrepancies due to the built-in models, particularly observed in secondary neutron energy spectra and specific reaction rates like $(\gamma, 2n)$ in ²³⁸U. In the end, this work verifies the photonuclear implementation in the selected OpenMC branch as a robust and accurate tool for high-energy photon transport applications.

Keywords: Photonuclear, Verification, OpenMC, MCNPx, FLUKA

1. INTRODUCTION

Photonuclear physics has recently gained attention across the nuclear engineering, medical, and accelerator communities due to its relevance in emerging applications such as photon-driven subcritical systems, fusion-fission hybrid concepts, medical isotope production, and high-energy radiation shielding. Accurate modelling of photon interactions with matter, including photonuclear reactions, is critical for predicting material activation, energy deposition, and secondary particle generation in photon-rich environments, and thus it has become a quite active field of research.

As in neutronics, Monte Carlo particle transport codes play a central role in photonics analyses; however, their predictive capability depends on the accuracy and verification of the implemented physics models. In recent years, substantial efforts have been dedicated to the verification and validation (V&V) of photon transport in OpenMC [1], an open-source, continuous-energy Monte Carlo code. Lund *et al.* [2] first implemented the photon transport capability, introducing detailed models for all major photoatomic interactions, namely Rayleigh scattering, Compton scattering, photoelectric effect, and pair production, together with secondary processes such as atomic relaxation and simple bremsstrahlung approximation models. Subsequent studies were devoted to verifying the photoatomic physics models. Works such as Peterson *et al.* [3], Zhang *et al.* [4], and Bae *et al.* [5] have demonstrated strong agreement between OpenMC, MCNP, and FISPACT-II in terms of quantities such as photon flux, dose rate, and

*antonio.cammi@polimi.it

deposited power. These verifications confirm that OpenMC photoatomic physics models provide accurate results across a broad range of energies and materials, reinforcing the reliability of the code for photon transport applications [6].

However, while the verification of photoatomic interactions in OpenMC is now well established, the same level of verification has not yet been achieved for the photonuclear physics, which includes reactions induced by high-energy photons such as (γ, n) , $(\gamma, 2n)$, and (γ, F) . Photonuclear reactions are essential for modelling photon-induced activation and neutron production in high-energy environments, yet only a limited number of benchmark and validation studies are currently available. Among these, the most recent and updated one is by Barber and George [7], being a key reference for photonuclear data testing. Additionally, Tuyet *et al.* [8] provided a validation of photonuclear yields and secondary particle spectra in TRIPOLI-4, DIANE, and MCNP6. Reproducing a similar work is out of the paper scope, extending beyond the current OpenMC capabilities, which does not model electron transport and associated Bremsstrahlung-induced reactions.

It is worth noting that recent studies, such as Sari *et al.* [9], have identified inconsistencies and potential bugs affecting several photonuclear data libraries (namely the ENDF7u contained in ENDF/B-VII.1 [10] and subsequent versions), in particular in the 4-20 MeV energy range when used with common Monte Carlo transport codes. Their analysis showed that simulated photoneutron yields are *systematically underestimated* compared to experimental data, often by a factor of two to three, depending on the target material and photon energy. These discrepancies are attributed to issues in the photonuclear cross-section evaluations and reaction threshold definitions. More recent libraries (JENDL-5, for instance) was found to be without with less inconsistencies. Nevertheless, this paper still adopts ENDF7u for the simulation workflow due to the limited accessibility of other nuclear data in the cross code: the presented analysis remains valid, as it focuses on a code-to-code verification performed under identical nuclear data and simulation conditions. In future analyses, the corrected nuclear data will be tested with the same methodology. In this context, this work contributes to the ongoing verification of photonuclear physics by performing a code-to-code comparison using the so-called *broomstick* problem [11], a canonical benchmark designed to isolate photon-induced neutron production. The simulations are carried out with OpenMC, FLUKA, and MCNPx, the latter two having well-established photonuclear modeling capabilities [12]. It is important to note that photonuclear reactions are not yet implemented in the official OpenMC release; therefore, all results presented in this work are based on a unofficial OpenMC version developed by Guy Stein [13] and accessible through GitHub. This benchmark provides a quantitative assessment of OpenMC photonuclear physics implementation relative to established codes and serves as a foundation for future development and validation studies in high-energy photon transport.

2. METHODS

The *broomstick* (or *pencil beam*) problem is a verification benchmark used to test the consistency of Monte Carlo particle transport codes and nuclear data libraries [11]. In its classical formulation, the problem consists of a monoenergetic, collimated source of particles directed along a very thin cylindrical target (i.e., the "broomstick") surrounded by a void region. The objective is to isolate single-collision events, enabling the direct estimation of the neutron production reactions, without the influence of secondary scattering or geometric effects. Each source particle is sampled at the cylinder's left end and travels parallel to its axis until it undergoes a single interaction with the target material. Following the collision, outgoing particles either leave the cylinder or are absorbed, allowing for tallies of reaction yields, scattered particle angular distributions, and energy spectra. In the present work, the broomstick concept is adapted for the verification of photonuclear reaction modeling: a thin cylindrical target of radius 10^{-4} cm and 2×10^3 cm length is irradiated by a monoenergetic, monodirectional photon source. This configuration ensures that all the particles (i.e., primary photons and secondary neutrons) interact only once. This case is implemented in OpenMC, FLUKA, and MCNPx under identical geometrical conditions (see Fig. 1), enabling direct code-to-code comparison of the photonuclear reaction rates and energy spectra of emitted secondary particles.

All simulations were performed using 1×10^7 source photons to ensure adequate statistical accuracy of

Figure 1. Representation of the broomstick problem: a monoenergetic photon beam is directed into a thin and long cylinder made of a specific target sensible to photonuclear reactions. Photoneutrons and photons crossing the lateral surface are scored.

the tally results.. The nuclear data libraries adopted for all calculations were from the ENDF7u release. To ensure consistent code-to-code comparison, electron transport was neglected in all Monte Carlo simulations by imposing a 15 MeV electron energy cutoff, as OpenMC does not model electron transport. This simplification is justified as the primary focus of this study is on photonuclear interactions and subsequent neutron production, rather than the detailed physics of the electron-photon shower at lower energies.

The primary quantities of interest (tallies) were defined and normalized per source particle:

1. The photon and neutron current exiting from the lateral surface of the broom per unit area.
2. The reaction rates within the target for key photonuclear interactions, specifically (γ, n) , $(\gamma, 2n)$, $(\gamma, n2\alpha)$, and photofission (γ, F) .

To verify the code performance across different physics regimes, three distinct test cases were defined and reported in Table I, each utilizing a different target material:

- a) A ^{238}U target, which allows for a comprehensive benchmark including (γ, n) , $(\gamma, 2n)$ and photofission (γ, F) reactions.
- b) A ^9Be target, selected to test the $(\gamma, n2\alpha)$ reaction channel.
- c) A target composed of ^2H (deuterium), primarily for testing the (γ, n) reaction.

Table I. List of simulated cases. Energies are chosen accordingly to the maximum cross section values.

Case	Material	Beam energy (MeV)	Density (at/barn/cm)
a	^{238}U	15	0.0047433
b	^9Be	5	0.06682
c	^2H	5	0.000539

3. RESULTS

The results for the three test cases are presented in Figures 2 through 8. Each plot comparing particle currents illustrates the energy-dependent distribution, the integrated total value, and the flux absolute difference of the OpenMC and FLUKA results with respect to MCNPx.

^{238}U (Uranium) Target

In the ^{238}U case, the photon current (Fig. 2) is well-aligned for energies above 5 MeV, but significant discrepancies appear at lower energies. The neutron current (Fig. 3) presents a complex spectrum, representing a superimposition of the three primary photonuclear mechanisms, dominated by photofission.

The results from OpenMC and MCNPx are in strong agreement. FLUKA simulated spectrum follows a similar shape, but its values are consistently lower across the energy range, leading to a lower total current justified in the following section.

Figure 2. Photon current crossing the broom’s lateral surface in the Uranium case.

Figure 3. Neutron current crossing the broom’s lateral surface in the Uranium case.

⁹Be (Beryllium) Target

The simulated photon current for the ⁹Be target (Fig. 4) shows excellent agreement among all considered codes, both in terms of energy distribution and integrated total current. Similarly, the neutron current (Fig. 5) exhibits consistent average neutron energies across the different simulations. Nevertheless, significant differences emerge in the neutron spectral shapes, reflecting fundamental discrepancies in the treatment of reaction kinematics. The dominant photonuclear process is the photoneutron reaction $\gamma + {}^9\text{Be} \rightarrow {}^8\text{Be} + n$ ($Q = 1.665$ MeV). OpenMC, MCNPx, and FLUKA all predict a pronounced high-energy peak at approximately 2.9 MeV, which is associated with the two-body kinematics of the (γ, n) reaction leaving the residual ⁸Be nucleus in its ground state ($E^* = 0$ MeV). For an incident photon energy of $E_\gamma = 5$ MeV, the maximum available kinetic energy is 3.335 MeV, resulting in a neutron

energy close to 3.0 MeV, in good agreement with kinematic expectations. In addition, OpenMC and MCNPx display a sharp low-energy peak around 0.25 MeV, which can be attributed to the (γ, n) channel populating the first excited state of ^8Be ($E^* \approx 3.03$ MeV). The large excitation energy significantly reduces the neutron kinetic energy to approximately 0.35 MeV, producing a distinct low-energy feature that is often intertwined with the $\gamma + ^9\text{Be} \rightarrow 2\alpha + n$ channel. The discrete appearance of these peaks in OpenMC and MCNPx suggests a simplified handling of excited states and multi-body final states. In contrast, FLUKA explicitly models the full three-body kinematics of the $\gamma + ^9\text{Be} \rightarrow 2\alpha + n$ reaction, in which the available kinetic energy is continuously shared among the three outgoing particles, resulting in a smooth neutron energy spectrum rather than discrete structures. Consequently, FLUKA reproduces a continuous spectral plateau while simultaneously capturing both the high-energy peak associated with ground-state population and the low-energy feature linked to excited-state emission, yielding a more physically realistic neutron spectrum. Overall, these differences indicate that while OpenMC and MCNPx accurately reproduce the average neutron energy and the dominant two-body channels, their simplified treatment of multi-body photonuclear reactions and excited-state kinematics introduces artificial spectral features, whereas FLUKA provides a more robust and continuous description of the energy partition. Despite these spectral discrepancies, the total neutron current remains comparable across all codes, with FLUKA predicting a slightly lower integrated value.

Figure 4. Photon current crossing the broom's lateral surface in the beryllium case.

^2H (Deuterium) Target

For the ^2H target, the photon current (Fig. 6) shows excellent agreement between all three codes across the entire energy spectrum. The neutron current (Fig. 7), however, reveals significant discrepancies among the three codes. FLUKA yields a flatter spectrum, with neutron energies concentrated between 1.25 MeV and 1.50 MeV. This spectral shape is physically consistent with the kinematics of the $\gamma + ^2\text{H} \rightarrow \text{p} + \text{n}$ reaction. However, the angular differential cross-section is strongly dominated by the Electric Dipole (E1) transition, following a $\sin^2(\theta)$ dependence. This dependence dictates that the neutron emission probability is maximal at 90° ($E_n \approx 1.42$ MeV) and nearly zero at 0° and 180° . In contrast, MCNPx predicts a distinct sharp peak at approximately 1.8 MeV, whereas OpenMC produces a distribution with the correct angular dependence centered around the same energy. Despite these spectral differences, the total neutron current predicted by OpenMC and MCNPx is in excellent agreement, while FLUKA gives a slightly higher integrated value. The discrepancies in spectral shape can be attributed to two main factors: (i) the average neutron energy in OpenMC and MCNPx is biased by a known issue in the photonuclear libraries, originating from a previous version of the NJOY processing system; and

Figure 5. Neutron current crossing the broom's lateral surface in the beryllium case.

(ii) the sharp spectral peak observed in MCNPx results from an internal inconsistency in the treatment of multi-body photonuclear reaction kinematics.

Figure 6. Photon current crossing the broom's lateral surface in the deuterium case.

Photonuclear Reaction Rates

Finally, the comparison of integrated reaction rates (Fig. 8) shows that OpenMC and MCNPx are in perfect alignment for all tested reactions. FLUKA, however, exhibits larger differences, most notably an underestimation of the $(\gamma, 2n)$ reaction rate in ^{238}U of $\sim 30\%$.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a verification of the photonuclear physics implementation in a development branch of OpenMC was performed through a code-to-code comparison with MCNPx and FLUKA, using the broomstick benchmark to isolate single-collision photonuclear events. The analysis focused on secondary particle spectra and integrated reaction rates obtained from ENDF7u data. Across all tested

Figure 7. Neutron current crossing the broom's lateral surface in the deuterium case.

Figure 8. Comparison of photonuclear reaction rates in the broom for different cases.

materials (^{238}U , ^9Be and ^2H) OpenMC and MCNPx showed excellent agreement in the integrated photonuclear reaction rates, including (γ, n) , $(\gamma, n2\alpha)$, $(\gamma, 2n)$, and (γ, F) , as well as in the total photon and neutron currents. The previously observed discrepancies in neutron energy distributions were clarified: in the ^2H case, both OpenMC and MCNPx produced spectra centered at the correct energy but with artificial peaks arising from simplifications in the treatment of multi-body photonuclear kinematics, while FLUKA correctly reproduced the smooth spectral shape. For the ^9Be case, the energies were in full agreement across all codes. However, OpenMC and MCNPx again exhibited discrete peaks linked to a two-body approximation, whereas FLUKA accurately modeled the continuous three-body breakup spectrum. In the ^{238}U case, all codes showed similar spectral behavior dominated by photofission, though FLUKA slightly underestimated the total neutron current and the $(\gamma, 2n)$ reaction rate. These results demonstrate that the photonuclear models implemented in this OpenMC development branch are robust and produce results consistent with MCNPx and FLUKA for most observables, while some remaining differences can be attributed to data-processing issues in the ENDF7u library and to simplified reaction kinematics in both OpenMC and MCNPx. Future work will extend this verification to updated photonuclear data once the reported inconsistencies in the evaluated libraries are resolved, and also perform the validation using the Barber and George benchmark.

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